

Supplementary table: Impact of each study-specific association estimate on the pooled SMD by influence analysis (Leave one-out method)

A) Outcome CIMT

Influential analysis (random effects model)

	SMD	95%-CI	p-value	tau ²	tau	I ²
Omitting Androulakis, 2014	1.1068	[0.8180; 1.3957]	< 0.0001	0.1796	0.4238	73.7%
Omitting Boyraz, 2025	1.2372	[0.8427; 1.6317]	< 0.0001	0.3778	0.6147	82.5%
Omitting Cansu, 2017	1.2231	[0.8312; 1.6150]	< 0.0001	0.3760	0.6132	82.6%
Omitting Delibasi, 2015	1.2443	[0.8544; 1.6341]	< 0.0001	0.3707	0.6089	82.4%
Omitting Emral, 2019	1.1750	[0.7965; 1.5536]	< 0.0001	0.3440	0.5865	80.0%
Omitting Evran, 2016	1.2130	[0.8205; 1.6055]	< 0.0001	0.3758	0.6131	82.5%
Omitting Imga, 2016	1.2596	[0.8749; 1.6442]	< 0.0001	0.3584	0.5987	81.8%
Omitting Kizilgul, 2017	1.1436	[0.7978; 1.4894]	< 0.0001	0.2812	0.5303	79.0%
Omitting Szychlińska, 2023	1.2283	[0.8350; 1.6216]	< 0.0001	0.3775	0.6144	82.6%
Omitting Tuna, 2014	1.2459	[0.8571; 1.6347]	< 0.0001	0.3690	0.6074	82.4%
Omitting Yener, 2009	1.3042	[0.9652; 1.6432]	< 0.0001	0.2663	0.5160	77.9%
Omitting Yener, 2011	1.2847	[0.9205; 1.6489]	< 0.0001	0.3165	0.5626	80.3%
Pooled estimate	1.2216	[0.8659; 1.5773]	< 0.0001	0.3311	0.5755	80.9%

Details on meta-analytical method:

- Inverse variance method
- Restricted maximum-likelihood estimator for tau²

B) Outcome: HOMA-IR

Influential analysis (random effects model)

	SMD	95%-CI	p-value	tau ²	tau	I ²
Omitting Androulakis, 2014	0.4855	[0.2965; 0.6745]	< 0.0001	0.0815	0.2855	69.8%
Omitting Arduc, 2014	0.5648	[0.3987; 0.7310]	< 0.0001	0.0486	0.2204	50.1%
Omitting Cansu, 2017	0.5146	[0.3200; 0.7093]	< 0.0001	0.0887	0.2978	71.5%
Omitting Delibasi, 2015	0.5253	[0.3327; 0.7179]	< 0.0001	0.0856	0.2926	71.0%
Omitting Emral, 2019	0.4458	[0.2838; 0.6079]	< 0.0001	0.0465	0.2155	55.0%
Omitting Ermetici, 2008	0.5346	[0.3494; 0.7198]	< 0.0001	0.0780	0.2793	69.8%
Omitting Evran, 2016	0.4783	[0.2913; 0.6653]	< 0.0001	0.0776	0.2786	68.4%
Omitting Imga, 2016	0.5095	[0.3137; 0.7052]	< 0.0001	0.0896	0.2994	71.5%
Omitting Karatas, 2003	0.5196	[0.3218; 0.7174]	< 0.0001	0.0901	0.3002	71.3%
Omitting Kim, 2020	0.5016	[0.3029; 0.7002]	< 0.0001	0.0911	0.3018	71.0%
Omitting Marina, 2017	0.5038	[0.3102; 0.6974]	< 0.0001	0.0880	0.2967	71.4%
Omitting Peppas, 2010	0.4932	[0.3012; 0.6851]	< 0.0001	0.0854	0.2923	70.7%
Omitting Szychlińska, 2023	0.5226	[0.3282; 0.7170]	< 0.0001	0.0874	0.2956	71.2%
Omitting Yener, 2009	0.4968	[0.3048; 0.6888]	< 0.0001	0.0861	0.2935	71.0%
Omitting Yener, 2011	0.5242	[0.3326; 0.7158]	< 0.0001	0.0852	0.2920	71.0%
Pooled estimate	0.5079	[0.3249; 0.6910]	< 0.0001	0.0811	0.2848	69.3%

Details on meta-analytical method:

- Inverse variance method
- Restricted maximum-likelihood estimator for tau²

HOMA-IR: Homeostasis Model Assessment for Insulin Resistance. CIMT: carotid intima-media thickness.

Supplementary Figure 1

Title: Funnel Plots evaluating the possible publication bias on the association between (A) carotid intima-media thickness and (B) Homeostasis Model Assessment for Insulin Resistance (HOMA-IR) levels in patients with non-functioning adrenal tumors.

Footnotes: Funnel Plots and Egger Test was used in order to evaluate the presence of possible publication bias.

Supplementary Figure 2

Title: Forest-plot illustrating the association between the standardized mean difference in (A) carotid intima-media thickness (cIMT) and (B) Homeostasis Model Assessment for Insulin Resistance (HOMA-IR) between patients with non-functioning adrenal tumors and control subjects, including only studies in which the effect of type 2 diabetes was ruled out (i.e. type 2 diabetes was an exclusion or matching criteria)

A

Outcome: CIMT

B

Outcome: HOMA-IR

Footnotes: The DerSimonian and Laird method, the conventionally used approach for random effects meta-analysis has been used for calculating the standardized mean difference (SMD) and its 95% interval of confidence (95% CI). The heterogeneity between studies was quantified using I^2 and τ^2 statistics.

Supplementary Figure 3

Title: Forest-plot illustrating the association between the standardized mean difference in (A) carotid intima-media thickness (cIMT) and (B) Homeostasis Model Assessment for Insulin Resistance (HOMA-IR) between patients with non-functioning adrenal tumors and control subjects, including only studies in which the effect of hypertension was ruled out (i.e. hypertension was an exclusion or matching criteria)

A

Outcome: cIMT

B

Outcome: HOMA-IR

Footnotes: The DerSimonian and Laird method, the conventionally used approach for random effects meta-analysis has been used for calculating the standardized mean difference (SMD) and its 95% interval of confidence (95% CI). The heterogeneity between studies was quantified using I^2 and τ^2 statistics.

Supplementary Figure 4

Title: Forest-plot illustrating the association between the standardized mean difference in (A) carotid intima-media thickness (cIMT) and (B) Homeostasis Model Assessment for Insulin Resistance (HOMA-IR) between patients with non-functioning adrenal tumors and control subjects, including only studies in which the effect of dyslipidemia was ruled out (i.e. dyslipidemia was an exclusion or matching criteria)

A

Outcome: CIMT

B

Outcome: HOMA-IR

Footnotes: The DerSimonian and Laird method, the conventionally used approach for random effects meta-analysis has been used for calculating the standardized mean difference (SMD) and its 95% interval of confidence (95% CI). The heterogeneity between studies was quantified using I^2 and τ^2 statistics.